

EFL Classroom Management at the Higher Secondary Schools

**In Partial Fulfillment of
the Requirements for the Degree MA in ELT**

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DECLARATION

I, Md Nazrul Islam, at this moment, declare that this work titled *EFL Classroom Management at the Higher Secondary Schools* is my original work and has never been submitted for an academic award to any university or higher institution of learning.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Md. Nazrul Islam', with a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Md. Nazrul Islam

CERTIFICATE

It is to certify that the dissertation entitled *EFL Classroom Management at the Higher Secondary Schools* was written under my supervision and is submitted for examination with my approval.

15.04.16

Prof. Dr. M. Maniruzzaman

(Supervisor)

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ABSTRACT

This study conducts "EFL Classroom Management at the Higher Secondary Schools" to determine the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement. The objectives are to: (a) determine the level of effectiveness of classroom management, (b) establish the level of learners' achievement, and (c) form the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level. The study adopts a quantitative paradigm with a cross-sectional correlation survey design and a sample of 35 respondents who participate in the study. A self-administered close-ended Likert-type (5-point scale) instrument is used to collect quantitative data through a questionnaire survey method, which is analyzed manually. The level of classroom management and learners' achievement is tested manually. The test results indicate a significantly low level of classroom management and a noticeably low level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level. The study finds a significant affirmative relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement. In contrast, the effect of predictor variables on learners' achievement is determined using multiple regression analysis, implying that it is a significant predictor of learners' achievement. The researcher, therefore, recommends that Principals and teachers may use the findings to improve classroom management practices for better learning achievement.

Keywords: *Principle, Procedure, Achievement, Classroom management, Responsibility.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Classroom management is a crucial factor of the total education system; although there are some problems with classroom management in many academic subjects, those are the critical area of research in general education in many countries (Doyle, 1990; Jones, 1996; Kagan, 1994; Tauber, 1997). Compared to the level of interest in general education, more attention should be paid to classroom management issues in language classrooms. There is little empirical research on classroom management in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in Bangladesh. This study will report on: a) classroom management difficulties that arise in Bangladeshi EFL classrooms when teachers teach English communicatively, b) how teachers conceptualize and attempt to deal with these problems, and c) what strategies can be offered to alleviate these problems.

1.1 Background of the Study

The research subject is essential because classroom management (CM) is vital for every teacher. Student English teachers (ST) report experiencing a handful of problems related to CM (Merç, 2004). According to Luo et. al. (2000), controlling classroom environments can be overwhelming for many graduate teaching assistants. Even teachers with 25 years of experience can face CM problems (Kyriacou, 1991). When the component of a foreign language classroom is added to the setting, the situation becomes even more problematic and uncertain (Fowler & Şaraplı, 2010). Teachers from all over the world are employing several techniques to deal with the possible forthcoming CM problems. Whether these strategies work well for their classrooms or fail is the research area for teacher education researchers (Altnel, 2006; Baker & Westrup, 2000; Tahir & Qadir, 2012). Building an effective training model is an urgent need to examine the CM issues in depth and identify ST management techniques that are best suited for effective language teaching. Therefore, this study will show an attempt to provide insights into the pedagogical strategies ST employs to plan, organize, and motivate student learning. Today's STs are likely to become tomorrow's professionals. An inquiry into helping ST become effective classroom managers will benefit their students and language teaching methodology courses provided in faculties of education. Furthermore, although it has found its place in teacher education research and language teaching methodologies, there has been little research to investigate the CM problems STs face while delivering lessons.

Therefore, this study is a promising one to explain and interpret the possible specific problems of ST related to CM and their coping techniques.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

This study is focused on the following objectives:

1. To identify steps for planning a classroom management concept.
2. To determine the level of effectiveness of classroom management at the higher secondary level.
3. To establish the level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level.
4. To establish the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level.

1.3 Justification of the Study

This study will provide reliable information to policymakers in the Ministry of Education, college owners, and college management teams who might use it in reviewing education-related policies. The study report shall enable the various practitioners within the college settings, including the principals, teachers, and students, to further their understanding of classroom management requirements and improve on the classroom management gaps. This research report will further help other scholars, researchers, and research users by providing literature and methodological guidance to build on further research, especially in areas related to classroom management at higher secondary schools.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

1. What is the level of effectiveness of classroom management at the higher secondary level?
2. What is the level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level?
3. What is the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level?

1.5 Limitations of the Study

Although this research is carefully prepared, the researcher is still aware of its limitations and shortcomings.

First, the research is conducted in the seven higher secondary institutions, which is needed for the researcher to observe all the institutions. It would be better if it would do most of the institutions in Dhaka City.

Second, the population of the experimental group is small, with only twenty-eight teachers and seven principals, and might not represent many of the teachers and principals. Third, since the questionnaires designed to measure the teachers' attitude toward using EFL classroom management strategies may give helpful information about the impacts, more evidence is needed of the teachers' actual EFL classroom management performance.

1.6 Definition of Terms

To deliver a comprehensive framework of the materials incorporated in this study the following definitions of terms are presented:

- *A **principle**-defines the positive attitude and expectations for long-term behavioral growth.*
- *A **procedure**-a specific activity by students and/or teachers that is directed at accomplishing something related to the rule.*
- *A **rule**-is developed from a guiding principle, is short-term in nature, and defines a general standard for observable behavior to support the principle.*
- ***Classroom management**-a systematic instructional process used by teachers to guide students toward successful rule compliance in the classroom, on the job, and in the community.*
- *Obedience-based models of discipline-uses punishments as deterrents, then creates fear that something bad will happen when rules are broken and provide rewards for doing what is expected.*
- ***Responsibility**-based models of discipline-requires teaching students the skills of decision making and providing opportunities to see appropriate behaviors in action from good role models.*

1.7 Structure of the Thesis

The researcher follows the following structure of the thesis:

- Introduction
- EFL classroom management
- Literature review
- Methodology
- Data analysis
- Conclusions and recommendations
- References
- Appendices

2. EFL CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

2.1 Introduction

Classroom management is the "actions taken to create and maintain a learning environment conducive to successful instruction" (Brophy, 1996, p. 5). It is also thought to integrate four areas: "establishing and reinforcing rules and procedures, carrying out disciplinary actions, maintaining effective teacher and student relationships, and maintaining an appropriate mental set for management" (Marzano & Marzano, 2003, p. 88). Classroom management should not be seen as synonymous with classroom discipline; it involves those other aspects mentioned above that are equally inherent to teaching. Crooks (2003) similarly sees a well-managed classroom as a relatively orderly room in which "whatever superficial manifestations of disorder that may occur either do not prevent instruction and learning or support them" (p. 144). The above definitions of classroom management have established an appropriate environment and order in the classroom so that teaching and, subsequently, learning can take place. A well-managed classroom can play an essential role in building a good society, nation, or a good man who will be the maker of society and nation. For this reason, a teacher is called a manager.

2.2 Background of the Study

Traditional classroom management practices have been centered on an educational curriculum for the last three centuries emphasizing teacher-centeredness, discipline, and one-directional transmission of knowledge to learners (Claassen & Marbach-Ad, 1998). However, according to Johnson & Johnson (1999), the trend in classroom management follows early thinking about children who are seen as idle and undisciplined creatures needing mental and physical training. Studies conducted during the 20th Century in different countries indicate a list of personal characteristics of successful teachers in classroom management (Gordana & Snezana, 2011) which includes warmth, kindness, friendliness, democratic attitudes, cooperativeness, consistency, openness of thought, and broad interests that are believed to impact positively on learners. Classroom management is therefore considered an issue dealing with students' behavior. Classroom management poses more significant challenges today than it was in the past when the traditional approach of reward(s) and punishment(s) was common in African schools (Scott, 1996). The present classroom management is geared towards realizing learning achievement (Kraus, 2016), and this is why teachers employ strategies like

extra written work, removal of privileges, suspension from class, and community services to stubborn learners.

According to Skinner's Operant Conditioning of Learning (1961), positive and negative reinforcement influences voluntary behavior. It implies that teachers who use positive reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something pleasant", that learner receives a reward, and teachers who use negative reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something good", then the unpleasant experience is removed from that learner. Skinner (1961) believes both conditions boost achievement, and it is ultimately up to the teacher and the prevailing situation to choose what outcome will work best to improve the learner's behavior and ensure the class can run as an efficient learning environment. The best way to understand behavior is to look at the causes of an action and its consequences (Skinner, 1961). From Skinner's positive reinforcement theory, Jones & Jones (2016) developed a non-adversarial model of creating a classroom that moves smoothly. In that, he came up with the three steps that include the positive practices, how the class can achieve from the positive practices, and taking notes of every day and every minute problem the teacher faces. It, he said, can lead to learners' achievement. According to Kraus (2016), classroom management refers to the teacher's ability to plan, organize and control students' behaviors. The actions and strategies are used to maintain order in the classroom (Burden, 2000). This author defines classroom management as the ability of the teacher to prepare, present, control, and manage the class record in a manner that leads to learners' achievement.

Although Burden (2000) suggests that learners' achievement is also paramount, he defines it as; meeting students' needs to obtain success and avoid failure. It is accomplished especially by exertion, skill, Practice, or perseverance. However, Stephen (2007) defines learners' achievement as the ability of a student to excel in academics, possess essential life skills, and have a sense of responsibility to contribute to society. In this study, learners' achievement is defined as the positive practices the learner has adapted and succeeded in doing. These practices include getting a good grade, time management, positive behavior change, class participation, attendance, smartness, and paying attention in class. However, learners in Bangladesh are accused of not observing class rules, negatively impacting their achievement. Research conducted in the United States of America (USA) finds that the teacher as a classroom manager is a broker of contradictory interests, one who "builds a working identity that is constructively ambiguous (Magdalene, 2011)." To emphasize her conviction that teaching

work is deeply personal, the author makes herself the subject of one of those studies. She concludes with an examination of how her view contrasts with prevalent academic images of teachers' work. However, studies conducted in the United Kingdom have shown that teacher aggressive classroom management scares students from learning (Patton, 1990). Learning achievement is high in the classroom with fewer disciplinary problems since teachers have to spend more time creating an orderly environment before instruction can begin (PISA, 2011). Interruptions in the classroom disrupt students' concentration and engagement in their lessons and, consequently, achievement.

2.3 Statement of the Problem

Classroom management is one of the critical components of any educational achievement. Higher Secondary schools achieve this due to teacher-classroom management ability and student compliance with classroom norms (Smith, 2009). According to the lesson assessment instrument of Gulu University Faculty of Education and Humanities, effective classroom management depends on the teacher's ability to prepare effectively, present the content consistently, control learners' behavior, and maintain class records. At the same time, the learner, on the other hand, is expected to comply with the class's rules and follow guidance from the teacher. Consequently, the learner will be able to get a good grade in exams, manage time effectively, portray positive behavior practices, participate actively in class, and maintain general smartness.

Classroom observation conducted by the Ministry of Education reveals that there needs to be more preparation scheme-of-work, lesson plans, and content coverage among teachers in higher secondary schools in Bangladesh. The report further exposes teacher-centered teaching, poor learning environment, and disorderliness in the classrooms is observed. It is believed to have resulted in non-compliance by learners who disrupt lessons, ignore assignments, have low concentration and participation in class activities, sleep in class and criticize teachers. It may be contrary to Jones & Jones (2012), who said that: "Teacher-good practices in the teaching-learning process attract corporation from the class hence learners' achievement." arising from the desirable situation highlighted above, this study is to answer the question of whether classroom management enhances learners' achievement in higher secondary schools in Bangladesh.

2.4 Methodology

The study population is 49. It includes all teachers and principals of studies in the seven higher secondary schools (colleges) in Dhaka City. Teachers are selected because they are directly concerned with classroom management, and principals of studies are mainly responsible for supervising teaching and monitoring class progress. According to Amin (2005), a representative sample gives results that can be generalized to the study population. The sample of seven colleges and thirty-five (35) respondents are selected from all categories of teaching staff and principals of study. The sample size determination is based on Watson, M. (2006) table for sample size determination. According to this table, there are given sample size(s) for the population. The researcher's target population is 49 respondents, including twenty-five teachers and seven principals of study, from seven selected higher secondary schools in Dhaka City. This sample is representative, and the researcher is confident of the study's generalization.

The researcher uses a questionnaire survey method for collecting data from respondents because the population is large and literate, and the information required is simple and easy to fill in the responses. This method can collect information quickly (Amin, 2005). The study employs a self-administered closed-ended questionnaire to collect data from teachers and principals of the study. Macmillan and Schumacher (2001) recommend a questionnaire if the researcher knows that the respondents will be able to answer the questionnaire. Closed-ended and scaled items are used. According to Macmillan and Schumacher (2001), the scaled items allow fairly accurate opinions assessments.

Similarly, it could solicit information from several respondents within a limited time. The quantitative data is processed, entered, and analyzed manually. The effectiveness of classroom management and the level of learners' achievement is determined. In this test, the determinant of the levels is based on the degree of variation of the responses from the expected value. For example, "Pearson product-moment correlation" determines the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement. In contrast, "multiple regression analysis" is used to determine which of the variables of classroom management is the better predictor of learners' achievement at the higher secondary schools in Dhaka City.

The following categories illustrate the main findings of the study: Classroom Management affects teaching regardless of subject or experience. Some participants, particularly EFL teachers at higher secondary schools, claim that the classroom management issues teachers encounter in the practicum are inevitably part of the teaching profession and not exclusive to language teaching. However, they know that it is something teachers have to confront and learn along the way, regardless of the subject they have to teach.

2.5 Challenges and Factors that affect Classroom Management

Regarding specific classroom management challenges that EFL teachers encounter in their practicum, many such challenges have to do with external, nonacademic factors that influence students' behavior or do not contribute to a good learning atmosphere in the context of secondary and higher secondary schools. One such factor is the high temperatures in class because the weather in the city is usually sweltering, and the classrooms are not equipped with air conditioning or ceiling fans. Noise from outside is another factor usually caused by different sources (people on the street, students in other classrooms, and cultural and social activities inside the school).

2.6 Approaches to Managing the Classroom

Regarding teachers' approaches to managing their classrooms, responses vary depending on the problem or situation. However, maintaining control is the most predominant approach among teachers across school settings. Most participants, including teachers and principals, claim that teachers make great efforts to control students' behavior in a class by establishing and reinforcing strict rules from the beginning and reminding students of the harsh consequences if they do not follow them. This approach typically involves talking louder to the students to regain their attention, writing notes in their notebooks so that their parents can see them, reminding students of who is in charge, intimidating students with negative remarks or low grades, assigning extra work in class to keep them busy, and at times getting into verbal confrontations with students.

2.7 Improving Classroom Management

The EFL teacher education program can help teachers improve their classroom management skills; participants in both settings emphasize that the program should offer them more opportunities to be involved in authentic school settings. However, most teachers claim

this can be achieved through different strategies, such as a course on classroom management with both theoretical and practical components and more specific observation.

2.8 Conceptual Framework

According to Skinner's Operant Conditioning of Learning (1961), positive and negative reinforcement influences voluntary behavior. It implies that teachers who use positive reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something pleasant," that learner receives a reward, and teachers who use negative reinforcement on the learner, that is, "if the learner does something good," then the unpleasant experience is removed from that learner. Skinner believes both conditions boost achievement, and it is ultimately up to the teacher and the prevailing situation to choose what outcome will work best to improve the learner's behavior and ensure the class can run as an efficient learning environment. The best way to understand behavior is to look at the causes of an action and its consequences (Skinner, 1961).

From Skinner's positive reinforcement theory, Jones & Jones (2012) developed a non-adversarial model of creating a classroom that moves smoothly. In that, he comes up with the three steps that include the positive practices, how the class can achieve from the positive practices, and taking notes of every day and every minute problem the teacher faces. It, he said, can lead to learners' achievement. According to Kraus (2016), classroom management refers to the teacher's ability to plan, organize and control students' behaviors. The actions and strategies are used to maintain order in the classroom (Burden, 2000). This author defines classroom management as the ability of the teacher to prepare, present, control, and manage the class record in a manner that leads to learners' achievement.

The framework shows the relationship between Independent Variable, classroom management, and the Dependent Variable, learners' achievement affected by the intervening variables. There is an assumed linkage between classroom management indicators (i.e., lesson preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management) and learners' achievement indicators, namely; getting a good grade, time management, understanding concepts, regular attendance, smartness, being attentive during the lesson, and handing in assignments. The implication is that; good classroom management enhances learners' achievement. Therefore, if teachers manage their classes well, then learners are more likely to achieve higher academically. According to the Operant Conditioning Theory of Skinner

(1961), classroom management indicators cause behavior problems that need to be addressed to realize learners' achievement. The framework also shows that the intervening variable indicators (teacher qualification, age of teacher and learner, gender of the teacher and the learner, experience of the teacher, learners' background, and learners' attitudes) affect the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables implying that when well controlled, learners' achievement is realized. This study can help the learners know their achievement levels as a class and adjust to classroom requirements for better learning. They can, therefore, pay attention in class, comply with classroom rules, and perform all tasks assigned to them by the teacher.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. Introduction

Classroom management is essential in EFL teaching at all levels, especially at the higher secondary level. Researchers, authors, and educationists gave different opinions about appropriately dealing with classroom management. Keeping discipline in class is a significant matter of classroom management. A widespread study identified the most successful classroom management techniques and practices (Kaliska, 2002). She says a classroom management method is needed to maintain optimistic student behavior.

Patricia Kaliska (2002) recommends communicate high expectations to students; use active listening skills; look for what is positive in a student's work; nurture student self-esteem; create rules that will accommodate all students, including students with handicaps or disabilities; provide positive reinforcement; deliver clear expectations, model effective leadership; be consistent in handling consequences; be fair; always respect student's feelings; avoid sarcasm, put-downs, and ridicule; believe that students are competent; be open to all points of view; be sincere; listen without judging; make parents allies; model the behavior you want; state classroom rules in favorable terms; always encourage children to do their best; keep parent-teacher lines of communication open at all times; keep children safe; belief in yourself as an exemplary educator; try new approaches; wait for appropriate response time; set clear, concise goal for instruction; give students choices to develop positive self-worth; get to know your students; start your day off with a positive ritual; provide a productive learning environment.

3.2 Classroom instructions

The study has also shown that classroom rules significantly affect student behavior. Therefore, teachers with practical classroom rules incorporated into their classroom management plan will more successfully maintain positive student behavior. A study shows that a classroom management approach is needed to maintain positive student behavior. Studies have also shown that classroom rules significantly affect student behavior. Therefore, teachers with practical classroom rules incorporated into their classroom management plan will more successfully maintain positive student behavior. Her study focuses on the following objectives:

1. to describe how behavior theorists influenced classroom management.
2. to identify approaches for managing student behavior.
3. to determine criteria for creating well-designed rules.
4. to identify steps for planning a rule management concept.

3.3 Behaviorist vs. Social Constructivist

Burrhus Frederick Skinner's philosophies can be related to the issue of classroom management. As a renowned learning theorist in the 1930s and 1940s, Skinner (Sprinthall, 1981) emphasizes his research on how the organism learns, regardless of its inherited potential, regardless of its stage of physical or psychological development, and often regardless of its species. Otherwise, he saw learning because of associations between stimuli and actions or impulses to act. Simple associations would accumulate into larger groups of learned associations. Skinner felt learning resulted from conditioning, like Pavlov's dogs' being conditioned to salivate at the sound of a specific tone.

Regarding the classroom, Skinner (Conte, 1994) states that by rewarding students for good behavior and ignoring or punishing wrong behavior, students would understand how to behave in a classroom environment. Behaviors that were rewarded would be repeated; those that were not would be avoided, and thus, a well-behaved class would result. This step-by-step conditioning process helped Skinner (Sprinthall, 1981) develop and test his first "teaching machine" in the 1950s. The teaching machine was a form of programmed instruction. At first, it was seen as a threat to teachers and their jobs. Reassuring the educators, Skinner announces that his programmed instruction is a learning aid, not a substitute for a human teacher. He also reassures educators that the children trained with the device will not become little mechanized robots but will more likely be able to reach their intellectual potential. Later, Skinner is credited with creating a revolution in education technology. Skinner's research on reinforcing stimuli also leads him to develop behavior-modification techniques in the classroom. Behavior modification involves training teachers to wait for their students to emit appropriate responses and then reinforce them quickly and consistently. This idea of behavior modification will, again, revolutionize technology in education.

In contrast, social constructivists tend to focus on the whole group and what is the best fit for the group (Arends, 1997). Previously, classroom management describes as "the

arrangement of students/groupings, materials, and furniture, and the movement of these over time, moving from one large group lecture to small cooperative groups or lab tables (Wolfgang, 2009). On the other hand, discipline is described by Arends (1997) as the correction procedures for misbehavior in the classroom. The following chapter discusses research studies that have been done that center around classroom management. Based on their findings, the studies are divided into preservice and first-year teachers, challenging student behavior, and urban environments. Research in the first section, preservice and first-year teachers, found that many diverse factors cause new teachers stress and frustration. All this stress and frustration stemmed from a lack of classroom management practices, leading some teachers to leave the profession altogether. The following section, challenging student behavior, found that some form of intervention is necessary to implement with students who express disruptive behavior.

3.4 Classroom Management

Jacob Kounin and his colleagues conduct substantial classroom management research during the 1970s. His work focuses on determining whether specific behavior settings and environmental conditions influence behavior. He also identifies a set of teacher behaviors and lesson characteristics, including smoothness, momentum, overlapping, and group alerting. These characteristics describe a teacher who knows what is always happening in the classroom and can deal with more than one issue or problem at a time. Classroom management facilitates student learning, allowing teachers to accomplish other critical instructional duties. Kounin (Conte, 1994) thinks teachers who can be that "aware" will be better managers of children in the classroom. According to Emmer and Stough (2001), Kounin became interested in a rather contemporary issue. He questioned whether managerial behaviors that work for regular education students have the same effects on students identified as emotionally disturbed in the same classrooms. His answer was "yes," at least in whole-class behavior settings in regular education classrooms. This research was an early indication that the inclusion of children with disabilities within the classroom was the right approach. Kounin's work then focuses on management research shifting from reactive to preventive strategies and from teacher personality to environmental and strategic management components. His work highlights the influence of classroom activities as a source of essential variations in student and teacher behavior. With this wide range of theories, Kounin's classroom management research helps identify many of the issues teachers are still facing in today's classrooms.

3.4.1 Psychology in Classroom Management

Maslow's research on the hierarchy of needs has also influenced effective classroom management. Helping students meet their needs is of the utmost importance to enhance student learning opportunities and maintain teacher longevity in the classroom. Maslow (as cited in Sprinthall, 1981, p. 327), an essential psychologist in motivation theory, has suggested a definite order in which individuals attempt to satisfy their needs. Maslow declares an "order-of-importance" that is universal among all humans. These needs must be met before the individual will be concerned with the needs of the next level of importance. In other words, basic survival must override other needs in this hierarchy. Herbert Grossman (Gordon, 2001) recaps students' basic needs and the order in which those needs must be met to produce well-balanced members of society. The following is a summary of Grossman's basis for student needs using Maslow's Need Hierarchy:

- *Physiological satisfaction: taking care of hunger, thirst, and rest.*
- *Safety: avoiding injury, physical attack, pain, extreme temperatures, disease, and psychological abuse.*
- *Nurture: receiving love and acceptance from others and feeling belonging to a group.*
- *A sense of personal value: experiencing self-esteem, self-confidence, and a sense of purpose and empowerment*
- *self-actualization: realizing one's full potential.*

The hierarchy of needs theory can be related to the school setting. According to Gordon (2001), school staff members may attend to basic physiological needs daily by providing breakfasts and lunches for needy students and, in some cases, making home visits to teach parents how to provide for their children's needs. Basic functioning in the learning environment is complicated until these physiological needs, like food, are met. Although meeting the second category of needs-those regarding safety issues may lie outside of the teacher's direct influence when students are at home or away from school, some of these needs can be addressed in the classroom. Good classroom management can help protect students from corporeal attacks by other pupils, hazardous environmental circumstances such as playing nearby with electrical equipment, and psychological abuse from peers or adults. Gordon (2001) believes the teacher can create a learning environment that is kind and respectful to meet the nurturing need.

Students will be better able to reciprocate genuine loving, caring behaviors toward others if the demonstration of affection is modeled for them in the classroom. Gordon (2001) states that the fourth needs category concerns self-esteem, self-confidence, a sense of purpose, and empowerment that directly relate to love and acceptance. If the students feel cared for and can express those emotions and behaviors, the student will continue to build self-esteem and confidence. The need for self-actualization can be fulfilled when the more basic needs have been met. All these theories are an intricate part of the history of classroom management research. Together the theories help build a foundation upon which we can continue to build our research on classroom management, including disabled students, reactive and preventative responses, and making value judgments.

This study explores classroom management tactics to help the improvement of the academic accomplishment of elementary school students. Classroom management has been a primary concern for teachers since there have been teachers in the classroom. A lack of classroom management affects both the teacher and the students. Studies show that some intervention positively impacts teachers, students, and the whole school climate. Teachers need to personally connect with each student in the classroom to make students feel comfortable and welcome. Research about classroom management has found that teachers who need more classroom management skills tend to react to classroom disruptions rather than prepare and plan for them. This lack of classroom management affects both students and the teacher. Studies have shown that if teachers can grasp classroom management early on in their teaching, they tend to leave the profession because of large amounts of stress (Arends, 1997). Emmer, Evertson, and Anderson (as cited in Marzano, 2003) indicated that classroom management training is set up for teachers at the beginning of the year, resulting in improved teacher and student behavior during the school year. Controversies in classroom management strategies stem from the duel between behaviorist and social constructivist points of view. Behaviorists tend to focus attention on the individual student.

In this study, there needs to be more classroom management strategies to combat students' disruptive behavior. The third section, urban environments, looks at the effects of classroom management in urban environments around the United States. The studies find multiple strategies to use with students in an urban environment, and teachers must take a while to get to know students personally in these urban areas. Trends and patterns in the body of research include the study design and the teachers' demographics. Most of the studies use some

form of survey or questionnaire to get answers from teachers. It is the most reasonable way to get a large amount of information from teachers who need to be closer together in location. The demographics of the teachers need to be more diverse. Most teachers that completed surveys and questionnaires were Caucasian females in rural and suburban areas' schools. The weakness in some of the findings came from the need for more diversity in observations. Many of the studies focus on a single classroom teacher. The findings are said to be transferable to other classrooms but do not prove transferability. It is hard to believe that students from a rural, predominantly white area will react in the same way as students who live in an urban, predominantly lower-class area to the strategies teachers are implementing for classroom management. Another area for improvement of the studies is a need for third-party observation and review. Many of the studies only include the immediate researchers involved. Some of the studies' strengths are the range of teachers who filled out and returned surveys to researchers. Some of the studies have returned as many as 300 surveys that included teachers from all parts of Florida (rural, suburban, and urban areas). When a study can include these demographics, it strengthens the transferability of the study to more locations. There are many aspects of classroom management for teachers to consider and think about, especially in their first few years of teaching. The most important thing for teachers to remember is the reason they chose to teach in the first place. Classroom management skills do not develop overnight; a teacher should have routines set up in the classroom and stick by those routines throughout the year. Again, take a deep breath and remember the reasons for becoming a teacher.

3.4.2 Positivity in Classroom Management

This paper aims to discover the paths that enable teachers to manage their work with students in the classroom. To be an efficient teacher means knowing what and how to motivate students to learn. As an efficient classroom manager, the teacher must have skills to plan and prepare the education process, know how to organize the teaching, and guide the class. Moreover, an efficient teacher must establish a positive classroom climate and working discipline. Also, the teacher should be able to evaluate the student's progress and self-evaluate his work. Examining teachers' classroom management skills in the Republic of Macedonia, research has been done on teachers in primary schools in the Republic of Macedonia. Instruments that will be used to complete the research and analyses are a questionnaire for teachers and educational policy analyses in our country to discover whether there is a concrete strategy for promoting and implementing classroom management on local and national levels. Analyses of results show a deficit of classroom management skills among teachers due to some

lapses in the initial education of teachers. To be efficient, a teacher must bear in mind that the following phases are essential to the teaching process:

- *It is essential to plan and prepare for the lesson.*
- *It enables the duration of the lesson itself, along with performance.*
- *It establishes a positive climate in the classroom.*
- *They are establishing a working atmosphere and discipline.*
- *It helps to evaluate progress and one's work.*

For all these to be realized successfully, conditions should be met:

- *The teachers must maintain a high level of attention to their students.*
- *They should encourage them (learners) and motivate them throughout the lesson.*
- *Activities realized during the lesson should be by the studying teachers are trying to achieve.*

A lesson thus set and organized improves the quality of the teaching and motivates the students to study. Thus, instead of a conclusion, researchers like to recommend the following:

- *The initial education of teachers should include further pedagogic education.*
- *Attention should be paid to self-evaluation because it is not used as a method in institutions; that is, it needs to provide better results.*

3.4.3 Teacher's Training

The already familiar phrases, such as the institutions in question should provide training programs, result in nothing. So again, the question reasserts itself, analyzing school conditions, says that the teachers need to be more motivated due to many reasons (their administrative engagements and the pressure from possible penalties). So therefore, if a teacher enters a classroom unmotivated, how should we expect students to be motivated – the teacher has no zeal for his work, which reflects poorly on the students and the whole of the education process. Of course, they will gain knowledge to last them the week, which does not bring anything to anybody. The answer to this question should be sought in how the state manages education affairs. We are only left to wait silently and see how and when the teaching process will be democratized while generations and generations of students are ignorant.

Being an effective classroom manager is a crucial component of successful teaching. Research has indicated that teachers are not satisfied with their credential program preparation in the classroom and behavior management. The study aims to determine if there is a correlation between the amount of management preparation teachers receive in their credential programs and their perceived confidence and preparedness in the classroom. Also, this study finds to discover if supplemental training is beneficial for beginning and experienced teachers. The literature review presented some common themes within this area of research: the importance of classroom and behavior management, teacher dissatisfaction with their knowledge of management strategies, and how the lack of these management strategies influences teacher job satisfaction. The researcher anonymously surveyed general education teachers and conducted a reflective analysis of the 28 participants' responses. The analysis reveals that although many participants are unsatisfied with their initial training, they feel prepared and confident when managing their classrooms. The variables that may influence teachers' preparedness and confidence are discussed. Within preservice credentialing programs, teachers must pass no specific test to ascertain if they are adequately prepared for classroom management challenges. Beginning teachers need to be given set guidelines regarding classroom and behavior management strategies. During their first year of teaching, they rarely have the time to acquire additional training in these areas. It is essential to know if teachers are satisfied with the classroom and behavior management training, they received during their credential programs. If a lack of management knowledge affects their confidence and preparedness in the classroom, it will be essential to remedy this problem. Teachers must be able to successfully accommodate the various behavior issues presented in today's inclusive classroom environment. This study's findings reflected similar data to studies discussed in the literature review. The participants' responses in this study were like the results Merrett and Wheldall (1993) gathered after interviewing teachers about their satisfaction with their credential program training. In both cases, many teachers who participate in the studies are dissatisfied with the initial management preparation offered within their credential programs.

The findings of this study also illustrate that additional training might positively influence teachers' confidence in the classroom and behavior management. Similarly, the research study conducted by Baker (2005) finds that it is essential for teachers to acquire some supplemental training for them to feel more capable of managing student behavior in the classroom. Baker's (2005) recommendations include diversifying additional management training for teachers to meet their specific areas of need, thus positively impacting their

confidence in the classroom. Overall, this study sought to highlight the importance of classroom and behavior management preparation and shed light on how this preparation influences teachers' confidence and preparedness in the classroom. Effective management is needed first to create a calm, focused atmosphere so the teacher can launch into a well-constructed lesson. As Wong and Wong (2009) affirm, "Classroom management overarches everything in the curriculum" (Wong & Wong, 2009, p. 80). Therefore, teachers who master classroom and behavior management create a positive learning environment where their students can flourish and succeed.

3.5 Technology in Classroom Management

Modern technologies have a remarkable role in revolutionizing the classroom setting. Therefore, it is incumbent on teachers to utilize strategies for effectively managing the change. The present study aims to discover English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers' views concerning classroom management. The connection between EFL teachers' demographic variables (age and years of teaching skills), computer attitude, and classroom instructional and behavior management alignments is discovered. The contributors to the study include male and female EFL language schoolteachers. The data for the current study are gathered through two questionnaires. The multiple linear regression analyses reveal that the independent variables of participants' computer attitude, age, and teaching skills are unsuitable behavioral and instructional management forecasters. The results also show that as the age and teaching knowledge of the participants increase, attitudes to computers become more negative. The current study investigates the relationship between computer attitude, age, teaching knowledge and behavior, and instructional classroom management methods incorporated by EFL teachers. The current study investigates the relationship between computer attitude, age, teaching experience and behavior, and instructional classroom management approaches incorporated by EFL teachers. The findings reveal that no demographic variables, i.e., teaching experience, age, and computer attitude, predicted the accuracy of teachers' behavioral and instructional management orientations. The present study's findings may be helpful to administrators charged with supporting the development of novice teachers. That is, they must understand how differences in demographic variables can influence novice teachers' future classroom performance. In this regard, they may benefit from the study's findings in gaining insight into the impact of teaching experience gained through years and CALL attitude on teachers' abilities to effectively manage classroom dynamics.

3.6 Theories and Surveys

Ample research findings support the influential protagonist that classroom management approaches play in increasing students' learning. This article examines to some extent which these teachers follow proactive classroom management strategies and if these strategies affect students' performance. Surveying students reveals that teachers apply classroom management strategies of the organization, teaching management, teachers' connection, and educator punishment–rewards (consequences) with fluctuating degrees. The Pearson relationship is applied in the results section amid students' attainment and every part of teacher management schemes. Finally, a confidential relationship is approved between teachers' assertiveness and students' performance. The results lead to implications for in-service training programs for EFL teachers. Many recent studies have shown that effective classroom management is necessary for a conducive learning environment (Hilary, 1991). In a conducive learning setting, students know what to do that is expected of them and how to achieve (Sanford, Emmer, & Clements, 1983). Besides, the literature shows that students achieve more academically in a well-managed classroom environment (Griffith, 2002; Wong & Watkins, 1998). Positive and negative attitudes of teachers are the central subjects of the study on classroom management. Teachers who use classroom management strategies more than others are more assertive. Shaver (2006) states that these strategies are: organization, teaching management, teachers' relationship, and teacher punishment–rewards (consequences) strategies. Canter and Canter (1976) assert that more affirmative teachers, who use a firm, assertive, and respectful tone, apply consequences, and deliver praise as expected, are demonstrated by pupils. While less-affirmative ones, who use an irresolute tone, fulfill penalties, and return conflictingly, cannot be demonstrated since students' prospects for modeling are uncertain. Given the presence of no detailed research covering the classroom management subjects in Iran and due to the repeated significance given to the powerful classroom management approach, this study intends to investigate such approaches among the EFL teachers at the high school level and their students' accomplishment to find solutions to the following study questions:

- *To what extent do EFL learners think high school teachers apply classroom management approaches?*
- *Is there any connection between relating to classroom management approaches and the EFL students' accomplishments?*

The questionnaire is composed of four subsections that address components of classroom management: organization (8 items), teaching management (11 items), teachers' relationship (10 items), and teacher punish–reward strategies (8 items). Respondents indicate on a five-point Likert scale (from much to never) how well each item describes their beliefs concerning their teachers' classroom management strategies. The process was not timed; participants typically completed it in approximately 10 minutes. High scores indicated a well-managed classroom and, thus, more assertiveness in teachers' behavior, while low scores indicated a less well-managed classroom and, thus, less assertiveness in teachers' manners. The validity and reliability of the translated questionnaire have been calculated through Cronbach α , which is, respectively, (0.91) and (0.94), according to Shawer (2010). Despite the attempts to conduct the current research, some limitations need to be acknowledged. Firstly, the study is limited in scope and conducted with a limited number of students who studied in high school. Thus, the study results must be verified with different groups of students and scopes. Secondly, this study investigates the students' opinions concerning their teachers; therefore, further research can be conducted using techniques such as observation, interviews, and other ways of data collection to verify the findings.

This paper is written to grow our stream of consciousness about the role of the teacher in classroom management and traditional methods. The researcher does not write the words of mind, but he writes the collected facts published by different important people who deal with these areas. The role of the teacher is vital in achieving outstanding results in the teaching and learning process. Traditional methods were widely used earlier, but with the growth of other methods, they need to be included. All that is said is going to be elaborated on in detail. By reading this paper does not mean that we will be the ones who will apply these methods in teaching, but we will try to avoid the traditional ones. Instead, we write what is accurate, different from what is said to be unimaginable. Someone can find much helpful information on different areas of teaching methods and methodologies.

3.7 Conclusion

As we see in the subsequent sections, the paper briefly explains the abovementioned methods and classroom management. Applying these factors in everyday teaching will lead us to an advantageous degree of learning and teaching methodologies. An endeavor as complex

as teaching can quickly become stressful and tedious when not managed appropriately. It can also become increasingly uninteresting when applying traditional methods in classroom management. Managing a classroom means simultaneously managing students' activities and behavior in a classroom setting, bringing something into the light. Different things should be done at the same time. It calls for continuous and frequent analysis. For an effective teaching-learning process, all teachers strive to gain more knowledge and experience in classroom management. If the teacher uses modern methods, the students are more likely to gain knowledge than traditional ones. After the necessary knowledge on classroom management is gained, then its implementation is what they must do. Implementing the techniques and methods gained is an alert that the goal is being achieved. A teacher's personality is what affects classroom management the most. Teachers should also possess some skills in psychology. Teacher's features like; flexibility and self-reflection help him/her provide better classroom management and a successful classroom in general. Being a teacher means also being able to understand student's problems and help them solve the problems. Finally, the researcher learns that teachers must know different areas to manage a classroom properly. Finally, applying modern methods makes the teacher's responsibilities easy.

Based on different sayings about methods, the researcher understands that teachers find it easy to continue using traditional methods rather than modern ones. The awareness of teachers and students keeps the traditional methods. Teachers should also possess abilities to understand natural phenomena that affect classroom management and teaching in general, such phenomena that students possess, such as student variability (psychological, cognitive, and cultural) and students' inner world (ego-states). By identifying such varieties, one can then deal with them appropriately. So, to be successful teachers, numerous teaching-related matters must be considered. These kinds of matters are all related to teaching methods or strategies.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher presents in this chapter the sampling, research design, study population, sampling procedure, data collection techniques, instrument, quality control, research administration procedure, ethical considerations, and data analysis.

4.1 Sampling

According to Amin (2005), a representative sample gives results that can be generalized to the study population. The sample of seven colleges and 42 respondents were selected from teachers and principals of the study. The sample size was determined based on Watson & Battistich's (2006) table for sample size determination. According to this table, there are given sample size(s) for the population. The researcher's target population is 42 respondents comprising 35 teachers and seven principals of study at higher secondary schools in Dhaka City. This sample is believed to be representative, and the researcher is confident of the generalizability of the study.

TABLE 1. Sampling Frame

S/n	Categories of respondents	Total populations	Sample size
1	Colleges	7	7
2	Principals	7	7
3	Teachers	35	28
Total		49	42

Fig. 1. Sample size, Primary data

4.1.1 Colleges

In selecting colleges, the researcher uses simple random sampling, particularly the lottery method, where the names of colleges are written on a piece of paper, folded, and picked randomly by the research assistants. The first seven colleges are picked from the sample. This method is the simplest to use and has no bias.

4.1.2 Classroom Teachers

Classroom Teachers are selected using simple continuous sampling from the attendance register booklets. Simple random sampling is a method employed to select a sample without bias from the target population (Amin, 2005).

4.1.3 Principals

Principals are selected using purposive sampling, while teachers and students are selected using simple random sampling from the attendance register booklets. In this method, each member of the population has an equal chance to be included in the study, and its advantage is that a representative sample will be used to reflect the view of the entire population (Amin, 2005).

4.2 Instruments

The study employs a self-administered closed-ended questionnaire to collect data from teachers and principals of the study. Macmillan and Schumacher (2001) recommend a questionnaire if the researcher knows that the respondents will be able to answer the questionnaire. Closed-ended and scaled items are used. According to Macmillan and Schumacher (2001), the scaled items allow fairly accurate opinions assessments. Similarly, it can solicit information from several respondents within a short time.

4.2.1 Transferability

The researcher is responsible for giving the correct presentations of the information the individuals give. It can be achieved by writing convincing narratives that capture many perspectives of a theme which will help describe the setting realistically, ensuring the study's transferability (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). Transferability is like external validity, how research findings can be transferred to other contexts (Bryman, 2016, p.384). The researcher has described the research context, theoretical perspectives, and research methods in a way that allows the reader to assess whether the research findings can be transferred to other contexts. When viewing reality as multiple and socially constructed, he has done his best to ensure that

the research has been carried out in line with the best research practices and to transfer the knowledge acquired during the course on research methodology in the master's degree into the whole research process.

To better certify that the research findings are transferrable to other contexts, the research has included thirty-five respondents than expected in ethnographic research; he has focused on two schools. He has also shared the research purposes with his interviewees, contacts within the schools, and researchers he knows (Bryman, 2016, p.384). This process starts with the research proposal shared with relevant contacts and possible research participants. He gets relevant and valuable feedback and advice from his supervisor and colleagues for the different processes. Finally, to give readers a possibility to assess if he has been able to carry out the research in line with best research practices, he has also carefully described the methods used here in this chapter and how these are in line with the literature on research methods.

However, it is also important to admit that when researching technology-assisted language learning and teaching, the transferability of conclusions arrived at can be challenging. This thesis has shown that people with students are extremely homogenous; however, there must be a universal understanding of computer-assisted language teaching and learning.

Validity: The validity of research instruments is assured by assessing the questionnaire items during construction. Validity is when the tool used to collect data corresponds with the variables in the study to produce accurate results (Amin, 2005). Questions are discussed with the supervisor, who provides technical input before administering them to the respondents. It is to clear any lack of clarity and ambiguity. The relevance of the questions where measures with the objectives of the study and scores against the classroom observation tool. The content validity index is computed as below:

$$\text{Content Validity Index (CVI)} = \frac{\text{Number of items rated relevant}}{\text{Total number items in the questionnaire}}$$

$$\text{CVI} = \frac{21}{25}$$

$$\text{CVI} = 0.84$$

It is supported by Amin (2005), who states that for any instrument to be accepted as valid, the average index should be 0.70 and above.

Reliability: Reliability is the extent to which a test or procedure of data collection yields similar results under constant conditions on all occasions (Amin, 2005). The reliability of the

questionnaire is ensured by pre-testing. The researcher gives questionnaires to the teachers and principals at the higher secondary level, different from the sampled schools in Dhaka City, for pre-testing. The test result is analyzed manually, confirming that the instrument is reliable since each variable has an item-scale correlation.

Credibility: Credibility narrates whether the findings are believable. To form the credibility of the outcomes, the researcher tries to ensure that the research is carried out in line with best practices. It has also been important to share the findings with the informants and other interested people from the research sites where the research is carried out. In this way, he can get confirmation that what he has understood and emphasized in the findings is in line with how members of the researched community understand their situation. This form of member validation, or respondent validation, has allowed him to share the research and the findings (Bryman, 2016, p.384). At the end of the research findings, he returned to his research sites, showed their data, and discussed with the participants in February 2016. In this way, the participants have an opportunity to their data and to confirm or disconfirm the data and provide new perspectives to the research process. In their feedback, almost all interviewees confirmed that the research reflects their opinions and presents the situation as it is on the ground in the two schools.

Conformability: To ensure the conformability of the research, the investigator critically assesses if his values and theoretical perspectives have influenced the research process and the conclusions arrived at to the extent that can make the research findings less trustworthy. It is reflected throughout this thesis. To allow readers to critically assess if his theoretical perspectives, presuppositions, and values have influenced the research to the extent that makes the findings less trustworthy, he has included a section describing his position as a researcher. It is also essential to recognize that no researcher can be completely objective (Bryman, 2016, p.384).

Dependability: The dependability of conclusions arrived at is parallel to reliability in qualitative research. To ensure dependability, the researcher has carefully written a comprehensive research log that documents and describes in detail the whole process of the research project. In addition, an anonymized version of the research log and all transcribed interviews will make available to assess if his theoretical approaches are justifiable and if the methods used are relevant and carried out according to the best research practices. In addition, it enables a sort of 'audit' of the research process, and the conclusions arrived at are more comprehensive than the criteria for evaluating reliability (Bryman, 2016, pp. 385-386).

Authenticity: To ensure the authenticity of the research, the researcher is, throughout the research process, and especially when synthesizing the findings and during the analysis, critically assessed to what extent different opinions and perspectives presented to him by the interviewees are captured and understood. He has also assessed if the research can help the research participants value different perspectives and understand their context better. It is done in discussions, and in one of the questions, the participants are asked to give anonymous responses (Bryman, 2016, p.386; Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, p.279).

It has been more challenging to assess if the research has sensitized and empowered participants to act to change their situation because the research process has been time limited. It may only be visible if the participants work after the research has been disseminated. The final thesis is submitted to the university. However, once, one participant will comment that some of the concepts described are advanced and difficult to understand. For example, the participant asks if an easy-to-read version of the thesis will be published. He is promised to write and share an easy-to-read version of the thesis and share this with all interviewees in addition to sharing this thesis. By doing this might be more likely that some people will have access to information that can inspire them to act (Bryman, 2016, p.386).

4.3 Data Collection

The data is collected from different higher secondary schools, which the investigator selects randomly. Next, he collects the institution name, sets it in alphabetical order, and collects the selected name.

4.4 Data Analysis

The quantitative data is processed, entered, and analyzed manually. The effectiveness of classroom management and the level of learners' achievement is determined. In this test, the determinant of the levels is based on the degree of variation of the responses from the expected value. For example, "Pearson product-moment correlation" determines the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement. In contrast, "multiple regression analysis" is used to determine which of the variables of classroom management is the better predictor of learners' achievement at higher secondary schools in Dhaka City.

5. FINDINGS

This chapter presented analyses and interprets the characteristics of respondents, the level of effectiveness of classroom management (lesson preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management), the level of learners' achievement, and the effect of classroom management on learners' achievement at the higher secondary schools in Dhaka City. All presentations are made in tables and figures and analyzed according to research questions.

5.1 Respondents' Characteristics

The information about the background characteristics of respondents at the higher secondary schools in Dhaka City has been presented in this section. The study is conducted among 42 respondents from 7 higher secondary schools (colleges) in Dhaka City. The variables presented in table 2 include the category of respondents, sex, and age. The qualification and experience of teachers and directors of study are also included in the table.

TABLE 2. Background characteristics of respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Valid percentage
Respondents	Principals	7	20%
	Teachers	28	80%
Sex	Males	22	83%
	Females	13	17%
Age	29-34	19	54%
	35-40	7	20%
	41-45	2	6%
	Above 45	7	20%
Qualifications of Teachers and Principals	Masters Degree	35	100%
	PhD	0	0%
Experience of teachers and Principals	Below three years	7	20%
	3-5 years	10	29%
	6-9 years	6	17%
	Above 10	12	34%

Source: Field data

Table 2 above shows that most respondents are teachers (80%) and Principals (20%), implying that most respondents were teachers (80%). The table also shows that most respondents were males (83%) followed by females (17%), implying that there were more males than females in the study, which suggests the enrolment in terms of gender. The table also shows that many respondents (54%) are in the age range of 29-30, followed by 35-40 years (20%), then those at the age of 41-45(6%), and lastly those aged above 45 (20%). It implies that most of the respondents, 29-30 years (54%), are more likely to be teachers, followed by 29-35 years (80%), who are more likely to be principals. The table further reveals the qualification of teachers and principals of study being the same (100%). Finally, it reveals the experiences of teachers and Principals of Study, with 34% having served above ten years and 29% below three to five years. It implies that most respondents have more than ten years of experience in the service.

5.2 Research Question One

What is the effectiveness of EFL classroom management at the higher secondary level?

Respondents are given four (4) areas to measure to determine the effectiveness of classroom management. These include teacher preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management. The ratings are based on the Likert scale (1932), and the results are presented in tables.

TABLE 3. Level of the effectiveness of teacher preparation

Teacher Preparation		Response				
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Some teachers use notes book only when teaching	6%	85%	0%	6%	3%
2	The classroom is congested and does not allow easy movement	18%	45%	23%	7%	7%
3	Some teachers use textbooks only when teaching	34%	60%	6%	3%	0%
4	Students are not comfortable with sitting arrangements in the classroom	18%	36%	28%	7%	11%

Source: Field Data

Table 3 shows that most respondents 85% agree that some teachers use only lesson notes books when teaching, 45% agree that the classroom is congested, 60% agree that some teachers use textbooks only when teaching and do not allow easy movement while 36% agree that they are not comfortable with sitting arrangements in the classroom. The percentage response scores on the level of elements of lesson presentation at the higher secondary level are presented in table 4.

TABLE 4. Level of the effectiveness of lesson presentation

Lesson Presentation		Response				
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Some teachers start teaching without reviewing the previous lesson	34%	37%	23%	0%	6%
2	Some teachers do not have full Knowledge of the Content being taught	14%	31%	28%	20%	6%
3	Some teachers' voices in not clear while teaching	17%	43%	14%	14%	11%
4	Some students are not actively involved in participating in the class	34%	31%	17%	6%	11%
5	Some teachers' handwriting is not clear on the blackboard	17%	54%	11%	3%	14%
6	The teachers always handle Learner's Contributions positively	23%	43%	20%	9%	6%
7	Students always do not like the lesson being taught	14%	57%	14%	14%	0%
8	Some teachers do not assess learners during lesson conduction	26%	34%	26%	3%	11%
9	Some teachers only copy notes with less explanation	34%	31%	14%	9%	11%
10	Some teachers do not share lesson objectives with learners in the class	29%	57%	0%	14%	0%

Source: Field Data

According to table 4 above, 37% of respondents agree that some teachers start teaching without reviewing the previous lesson, 57% agree that some teachers do not share lesson objectives with learners, and 31% agree that some teachers need complete knowledge of what they teach. The table further shows that 43% of respondents agree that some teachers' voices

could be more unmistakable while teaching, 34% strongly agree that some students are not actively participating in class activities, and 54% agree that some teachers' handwriting needs to be clarified. It is also revealed in the table that 57% of respondents agree that students always do not like the lesson being taught, 43% agree that the teacher always does not handle learners' contribution positively, 34% agree that some teachers do not assess learners during the lesson and finally, 34% strongly agree that some teachers only copy notes with less explanation.

The presentation of the percentage scores of responses on the elements of class control at the higher secondary level is in table 5.

TABLE 5. Level of the effectiveness of class control

Class Control		Response				
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Some students disturb others during lessons and discussion	20%	43%	9%	17%	11%
2	There are unnecessary movements by some learners during learning	21%	29%	25%	14%	11%
3	Some teachers do not attend to the individual learner during teaching	14%	58%	14%	7%	7%
4	The teacher does not supervise group activities	23%	23%	23%	11%	20%
5	Some teachers are not competent and presentable in the class	43%	29%	14%	14%	0%
6	Some teachers report late to class	43%	57%	0%	0%	0%
7	There are no rules specifically for the classroom that they have seen	29%	29%	18%	14%	11%

Source: Field Data

The study result in table 5 shows that 29% strongly agree and 29% agree that there is no rule specifically for the class that they have ever seen, 43% agree that some students disturb others during lessons and discussions, 29% agree that there are unnecessary movements by learners during a lesson and 58% agree that some teachers do not attend to individual learners

during a lesson. The table further shows that 23% strongly agree and 23% agree that the teacher does not supervise class activities, 43% strongly agree that some teachers are not intelligent and presentable in the classroom, and 57% agree that some teachers consistently report late to the classroom.

Figure 2 gives the percentage response distribution on the elements of record management at the higher secondary level.

Fig. 2.: Level of the effectiveness of record management, Field Data

According to figure 2 above, 46% agree that teachers do not make roll calls daily, and 43% agree that the class teacher does not properly keep records of assessment scores. All the elements of classroom management measured have a significantly low level of effectiveness since the distribution of responses in support of a low level is above the expected value that would determine the equal distribution of responses in all the categories. It is an indication that there needs to be a significantly higher level of effectiveness of classroom management at the higher secondary level in Dhaka City.

5.3 Research Question Two

The question “What is the level of EFL learners’ achievement at the higher secondary level?”

Findings of all the elements of learners’ achievement are presented in figure 3 and analyzed.

Fig. 3.: Level of learners' achievement, Field Data

According to figure 3 above, 57% of respondents agree that students do not get very high marks on tests and exams, 25% agree that some students come late to class, and 46% agree that some do not attend lessons. The table also reveals that 29% agree that some students sleep in class sometimes, 54% agree that some students talk during a lesson, and 36% agree that some students do not turn in assignments for marking. All the elements of classroom management measured had a significantly low level of effectiveness since the distribution of responses in support of a low level is above the expected value that would determine the equal distribution of responses in all the categories. In addition, it indicates a significantly low level of learners' achievement at the higher secondary level in Dhaka City.

5.4 Research Question Three

The question states, "What is the relationship between EFL classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level?"

The researcher uses Pearson correlation statistics to measure the "relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement" and to determine the hypothesis that: "There is no significant relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level." The relationships of all four elements of classroom management (i.e., lesson preparation, lesson presentation, class control, and record management) have been measured against learners' achievement. Multiple regression analysis has been used to determine learner achievement predictor variables. All the variables except teacher preparation are significant predictors of learners' achievement at a 5% significance level.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusions

The conclusions are made in line with the study objectives supported by the analyzed data. It includes (1) the level of classroom management, (2) the level of learners' achievement, and (3) the relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level in Dhaka City.

The study reveals a low level of classroom management at the higher secondary level, and teachers' ineffectiveness in planning, employing teaching methodologies, class control, and record management is very high. The finding further reveals a deficient level of learners' achievement, characterized by low academic performance in tests and examinations, poor time management, lack of attention during lesson conductions, and poor class hygiene management. Finally, the finding reveals a significant positive relationship between classroom management and learners' achievement at the higher secondary level.

6.2 Recommendations

The findings of this study can help college administrators, teachers, and students understand classroom management factors and how they affect learning achievement. Principals should use the findings from this study to devise practical supervision approaches to the teaching and learning process, set achievement targets for individual classes, and provide capacity development training for teachers in classroom management. Teachers should be able to revisit how they manage their classrooms using the findings of this study. They should, therefore, be able to effectively plan, teach and evaluate the performance of their learners based on the pre-set achievement goal(s). Engagement of learners in classroom management practices such as setting self-goals and class rules will motivate learners to own what they have made and implement it accordingly. Finally, this study can help the learners know their achievement levels as a class and adjust to classroom requirements for better learning. They can, therefore, pay attention in class, comply with classroom rules, and perform all tasks assigned to them by the teacher.

6.3 Further Research

The study looks to discover a possible theme that can be explored further in subsequent studies. From the interviews, the teacher's use of classroom rules is advantageous for EFL

classroom management. It is due to the respect it generates in the students and the fact that they immediately understand what the teacher requires.

However, further research will need to be expanded to verify the veracity of such a claim. Firstly, for any claim to be generalizable, the study must incorporate a much larger sample of teachers teaching across different age groups and perhaps from different institutions. Further research can incorporate female participants to see whether female native English teachers share the same experiences. Moreover, methods of triangulation can be used to counter threats to validity. For example, data triangulation will strengthen the study's validity, as distinguished by Denzin (1988). As well using interviews, observations can be done and questionnaires for the students if this is ethically approved. Also, they opine that this policy needs to be implemented by teachers or enforced by the administration. A developed study may lead to a rethinking of this institutional policy. The push to recruit native English speakers may be supported by research, as previously discussed. However, with the importance of classroom management in student achievement, if a further study yields similar results, recruiters may have something to ponder.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix I: Questionnaires

Questionnaire for Principals

Dear respondent,						
I am Md. Nazrul Islam carrying out a study of EFL classroom management at the higher secondary level. Please would you take some time to complete this questionnaire? It is being used to collect information for study purpose. Your view will be highly respected and kept confidential. You are free to express your view with respect to the below questions.						
Biographic information						
01	Name of your college		04	Sex		
02	Your qualification		05	Years in service		
03	Age		06	No. periods a week		
For the below questions scale (Likert, 1932) , tick the appropriate box to indicate your answer i.e.						
Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree (SD)						
No	Question	Answer				
1	Some teachers use notes book only when teaching	SA	A	N	DA	SD
2	Some teachers use textbooks only when teaching	SA	A	N	DA	SD
3	Some teachers start teaching without reviewing the previous lesson	SA	A	N	DA	SD
4	Some teachers handwriting is not clear on the blackboard	SA	A	N	DA	SD
5	Level of lesson preparation very high	SA	A	N	DA	SD
6	Some teachers do not share lesson objectives with learners in the class	SA	A	N	DA	SD
7	Level of lesson presentation very high	SA	A	N	DA	SD
8	Some teachers do not have full Knowledge of Content being taught	SA	A	N	DA	SD
9	Some teachers' voice is not clear while teaching	SA	A	N	DA	SD
10	Some students are not actively involved to participate in the class	SA	A	N	DA	SD
11	Level of class control very high	SA	A	N	DA	SD
12	Record of assessment scores are properly kept by the class teacher	SA	A	N	DA	SD
13	Students always do not like the lesson	SA	A	N	DA	SD
14	The teachers always handle Learner's Contribution positively	SA	A	N	DA	SD
15	Some teachers do not assess learners during lesson conduction	SA	A	N	DA	SD
16	Some teachers only copy notes with lesson explanation	SA	A	N	DA	SD
17	Level of learners' achievement very high	SA	A	N	DA	SD
18	Some students sleep in class sometimes	SA	A	N	DA	SD
19	Some students disturb others during lesson and discussion	SA	A	N	DA	SD
20	Some students talk in class during lesson	SA	A	N	DA	SD
21	Roll calls are not made daily	SA	A	N	DA	SD
22	Supervision of group activities are not done by the teacher	SA	A	N	DA	SD
23	Students do not get very high marks in tests and exams	SA	A	N	DA	SD
24	Some teachers are not smart and presentable in the class	SA	A	N	DA	SD
25	Some teachers report late to class	SA	A	N	DA	SD

Thank you.

Questionnaire for Teachers

Dear respondent,						
I am Md. Nazrul Islam carrying out a study of EFL classroom management at the higher secondary level. Please would you take some time to complete this questionnaire? It is being used to collect information for study purpose. Your view will be highly respected and kept confidential. You are free to express your view with respect to the below questions.						
Biographic information						
01	Name of your college		04	Sex		
02	Your qualification		05	Years in service		
03	Age		06	No. periods a week		
For the below questions scale (Likert, 1932) , tick the appropriate box to indicate your answer i.e. Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral(N), Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree (SD)						
No	Question	Answer				
1	Some teachers use notes book only when teaching	SA	A	N	DA	SD
2	Some teachers use textbooks only when teaching	SA	A	N	DA	SD
3	Record of assessment scores are properly kept by the class teacher	SA	A	N	DA	SD
4	I am not comfortable with sitting arrangements in the classroom	SA	A	N	DA	SD
5	Some teachers start teaching without reviewing the previous lesson	SA	A	N	DA	SD
6	Sometimes I come late to class	SA	A	N	DA	SD
7	Some teachers do not have full Knowledge of Content being taught	SA	A	N	DA	SD
8	Some teachers' voice in not clear while teaching	SA	A	N	DA	SD
9	Some students are not actively involved to participate in the class	SA	A	N	DA	SD
10	Some teachers' handwriting is not clear on the blackboard	SA	A	N	DA	SD
11	The classroom is congested and does not allow easy movement	SA	A	N	DA	SD
12	Some students do not turn in assignment for marking	SA	A	N	DA	SD
13	Some students talk in class during lesson	SA	A	N	DA	SD
14	The teachers always handle Learner's Contribution positively	SA	A	N	DA	SD
15	Some teachers do not assess learners during lesson conduction	SA	A	N	DA	SD
16	Some teachers only copy notes with less explanation	SA	A	N	DA	SD
17	There is no rules specifically for the classroom that I have seen	SA	A	N	DA	SD
18	Roll calls are not made on a daily basis	SA	A	N	DA	SD
19	Some students disturb others during lesson and discussion	SA	A	N	DA	SD
20	There are unnecessary movement by some learners during learning	SA	A	N	DA	SD
21	Some teachers do not attend to individual learner during teaching	SA	A	N	DA	SD
22	Supervision of group activities are not done by the teacher	SA	A	N	DA	SD
23	Some students do not attend lesson	SA	A	N	DA	SD

Thank you.

Appendix II: Map of Dhaka City

The study was conducted in Dhaka City

